

Phendata analysis for Chr7 by JW

R Markdown

This is an R Markdown document. Markdown is a simple formatting syntax for authoring HTML, PDF, and MS Word documents. For more details on using R Markdown see <http://rmarkdown.rstudio.com>.

When you click the **Knit** button a document will be generated that includes both content as well as the output of any embedded R code chunks within the document. You can embed an R code chunk like this:

```
##
## >=====
## This version of PhenStat includes *FEWER* functions than the previous ones
## You *still* can use the previous functions by using ':::'. For example :
## PhenStat:::boxplotSexGenotype or PhenStat:::FisherExactTest
## *** Want to know what is new in this version? run PhenStat:::WhatIsNew()
## >=====

## [1] "C:/Users/wottoj/offline/killonedrive/chr7_phenstat"

## Warning:
## Dataset's 'Batch' column is missed.
## You can define 'dataset.colname.batch' argument to specify column for the batch effect modeling.

## Information:
## Dataset's 'Genotype' column has following values: 'C57BL/6J', 'Chr7'

## Information:
## Dataset's 'Sex' column has following value(s): 'Female', 'Male'

## Information:
## Dependent variable: 'Weights.Heart.Weight'.

## Information:
## Perform all MM framework stages: startModel and finalModel.

## Information:
## Method: Mixed Model framework.

## Information:
## Equation: 'withWeight'.

## Information:
## Calculated values for model effects are: keep_Batch=FALSE, keep_EqualVariance=FALSE, keep_Weight=TRUE
```

```

##
## Test for dependent variable:
## *** Weights.Heart.Weight ***

##
## Method:
## *** Mixed Model framework ***

## -----

## Model Output

## -----

## Final fitted model: Weights.Heart.Weight ~ Genotype + Weight

## Was batch significant? FALSE

## Was variance equal? FALSE

## Genotype p-value: 8.141081e-02

## Genotype effect: 9.012320e+00 +/- 5.195426e+00

## Was there evidence of sexual dimorphism? no (p-value 9.762432e-02)

## Genotype percentage change Female: 8.34%

## Genotype percentage change Male: 8.34%

##
## -----

## Classification Tag

## -----

## With phenotype threshold value 0.01 - no significant change

##
## -----

## Model Output Summary

## -----

##           Value Std.Error   t-value   p-value
## (Intercept) -0.07922578 11.5828036 -0.006839949 9.945911e-01
## GenotypeChr7  9.01231987  5.1954258  1.734664328 9.379772e-02
## Weight        4.09891313  0.4497774  9.113203483 7.173651e-10

```

““

Note that the `echo = FALSE` parameter was added to the code chunk to prevent printing of the R code that generated the plot.